

The unusual kinetics of lactate dehydrogenase of *Schistosoma mansoni* and their role in the rapid metabolic switch after penetration of the mammalian host

This file was originally made by Olivier Martin and updated by Jurgen Haanstra for the Zenodo files. The original file referred to folders with files, but that folder structure is not seen in Zenodo. Note that commands in models may refer to the files when they were in their original folders. The original structure can be restored through the “./” headings of the sections in this README file.

Dependencies

- Python, Jupyter Notebooks and the following modules:
 - abcpmc
 - numpy
 - pysces
 - matplotlib
 - seaborn
 - roadrunner
 - scipy
 - pandas
 - progressbar
- R, Rstudio and the following packages:
 - ggplot2
 - data.table
 - ggpubr
 - cowplot
 - scales
 - stringr

Commands to Replicate Results

```
# 1. Estimation of glycolysis parameters using ABC
python abc_martin8.py

# 2. Estimates distributions of rates and concentrations
python distributions.py
```

3. Open `plots.Rmd` in RStudio and knit to HTML.
4. Open `mammalian_hexokinase.ipynb` and run in Jupyter.

Description of Files and Folders

./data

Data used for parameter estimation of LDH or glycolysis model

abc_martin* (Approximate Bayesian Computation (ABC) parameters files)

- Parameters used for ABC script (abc.py)

flux* (Fluxes of schistosomal glycolysis)

- flux3.csv
 - Metabolism of cercariae in water in the presence of high glucose (5.5mM) can be estimated from the data on cercarial bodies during transformation (Table 1, Horemans 1992) and the data on schistosomula (Fig 2, Horemans 1992).
 - There is no glucose under physiological conditions (the 0.05 mM in the published tables was just a tracer amount of radioactive glucose to determine the ratio of lactate and CO₂ produced from the degraded glycogen reserves)

NEW_LDH* (Kinetic data acquired from Lodewijk Tielens)

- NEW_LDH.csv
- NEW_LDH.xlsx (correction factor calculations are in there)
- NEW_LDH_MEAN.csv (mean of replicates are computed)

./notebook

- plots.Rmd: R notebook file used to plot figures
- ./notebooks/mammalian_hexokinase.ipynb: Jupyter Notebook used to generate ./img/figure_S6 (this is Fig S7 in the final manuscript)

./models

Glycolysis models are called Martin8. psc files are [PySCeS](#) model files

and xml to [SBML](#). Comes in three flavours:

- tc for time-course (glycogen is unfixed)
- ss for steady-state (glycogen is fixed)
- gp for glucose-pulse (glycogen is unfixed, and glucose pulse after 2000 seconds)

./output

Approximate Bayesian Computation (./scripts/abc.py)

- abc_errors_*.txt
 - Errors, thresholds, acceptance ratios
- abc_errors_*.txt
 - Last estimation of glycolytic parameters posterior distributio

Distribution of rates and species in different extracellular glucose conditions.

Outputed by `distributions.py`

Columns are named according to the following conventions:

- `id`:
 - Iteration number
 - Can be used to match parameters with values
- `modelname`:
 - `both`: wildtype LDH that is sensitive to both ATP and FBP
 - `atp`: only ATP-inhibited
 - `fbp`: only FBP-activated
 - `none`: non-allosteric
 - `noldh`: no LDH
- `Time`:
 - For `tc.csv` files, corresponds to time point in minutes
- `valid`
 - Validity of steady-state
 - If `False`, then values correspond to the last point of a time-course of 7 days.

Files named according to the following conventions:

- `blood_*` Extracellular glucose concentration is set to 5.5 mM
- `water_*`
 - Extracellular glucose concentration is set to 0.0 mM
- `params`
 - Models parameters used to generate rates and concentrations
- `values`
 - Rates and concentrations
- `tc`
 - Time course
- `ss`
 - Steady-state

./scripts

- `abc.py`
 - Python script that allows estimations of kinetic models using Approximate Bayesian Computation.
 - Takes one argument, a python file formatted exactly like `abc_martin8.py` .
 - Output is found in `abc_*`
- `distributions.py`
 - Estimates distribution of species and rates by sampling parameters
- `distributions_functions.py`
 - Collection of Python functions used in `distribution.py`

- `distributions_params.py`
 - Collection of parameters used in `distribution.py`
- `functions.R`
 - Collection of R functions used in `plots.Rmd`